
Potential Indonesian Kenaf Varieties (Kenafindo) as Textile Raw Materials

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Abstract

Kenaf is a natural fiber-producing plant that is widely used as a raw material for making fiberboard (door-trim, car interior), particle board, fiber drain, geo-textile and high-quality paper. Kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus*) produces fiber from its trunk, which is then classified as a bast fiber. Two new superior varieties of kenaf, Kenafindo 1 and Kenafindo 2 have the advantage of being less sensitive to the length of the daylight. Potential production of Kenafindo 1 and Kenafindo 2 is 2.5-4.5 tons of dry fiber / ha with fiber length of 225-235 cm, white fiber color (grade A), and fiber smoothness (smooth). Kenaf fiber lignin levels of Kenafindo 1 and Kenafindo 2 varieties were 9.36% and 7.26% respectively. Kenaf fiber Kenafindo 1 and Kenafindo 2 varieties have the opportunity as textile raw materials for garments. There are several advantages for using kenaf fiber as textile raw materials including good absorption, fire resistance and antimicrobial properties.

Keywords: natural fiber, kenaf, potential, textile

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1. Introduction

The textile and textile products industry (TPT industry) is one of the pioneering industries and the backbone of the industrial sector in Indonesia. However, the import of cotton fiber, the textile raw material, reached up to 450 thousand tons in 2016 (Dirjen Perkebunan, 2017). During the past decade, the government through the Ministry of Industry tried to explore the potency of Indonesia's natural resources known as SANT (Non-Textile Natural Fiber) such as pineapple fiber, kapok fiber, coconut fiber, banana fiber, fiber from doyo caterpillar and so on, to be used as raw material for textiles and textile products (Sukardan et al., 2016).

Natural fibers are obtained from nature, plants, animals and mineral sources. Natural fibers are categorized into two main groups: cellulose or plant fibers; and animal protein or fiber. Fiber is used as raw material for making yarn, which is then woven, knitted or tied into a cloth used in clothing production. Fiber-producing plants are divided into three groups, namely fruit fiber plants, stems, and leaves, based on plant parts that produce fiber. Kenaf is a plant that belongs to the group of stem fibers because kenaf fibers are obtained in the bark (Sudjindro, 2011). Kenaf fiber has been developed

in Indonesia since 1978 through the People's Sack Fiber Intensification (ISKARA) program. At that time, kenaf fiber was only used as a gunny sack (Aghnat Baizura Hapidh, 2017)., Kenaf fibers are classified as sclerenchymal fibers, in which the highest fiber content (75%) is found in the lower stem and known as thick-walled cells containing lignin. This fiber functions mechanically so that it is resistant to stress due to withdrawal and bending, pressure and compression without causing damage to the thick-walled cells in this part of the plant (Suliyanthini, 2016).

The kenaf plant has two fiber types: the outer bark or bast portion (40% of the plant) and the inner woody core material (60%) (Zhang, 2003). Kenaf fibres are produced by separating the core of kenaf from the fibrous outer layers. The extracted layers are chemically or microbiologically retted to convert into fibres. Retting is a wet process by which bundles of cells in the outer layer of the stalk is separated from the non-fibrous material by removing pectins and other gummy substances. Retting aims to eliminate components that attach fibers, such as pectin, hemicellulose, lignin, and other impurities without damaging cellulose fibers (Yu and Yu, 2010; Jamil. H and Marjani, 2018).

Kenaf fiber has several advantages including good absorption, fire resistance and antimicrobial properties, so it can be used as a textile raw material for various purposes. Kenaf fiber is also not affected by moisture and insulated against noise and heat (Ramakrishna G et al., 2018). Kenaf fibres are found as useful applications in making knit and woven textiles. These fibers blend very well with cotton, and find its commercial and healthy applications in making outerwear due to its natural absorbency and fire-retardant abilities (Fibre2fashion, 2019).

Kenaf fiber also has several disadvantages when used as a textile raw material. Kenaf bundle fibers are rather stiff, and the single fibers are also relatively short for textile yarn manufacturing processes. These unfavorable properties have inhibited the production of high-quality yarns and fabrics containing kenaf (Zhang, 2003). Therefore, some research have provide combined kenaf fiber with cotton fiber to be proceeded into yarn as textile raw material (Ramakrishna G et al., 2018). The combination of kenaf fiber and other types of fiber plants makes the fiber more qualified and suitable to be used as textile raw materials. This paper elaborates the potency of two Indonesian kenaf varieties (Kenafindo 1 and 2) as textile raw materials and discusses the characteristics of fiber quality and chemical properties of these varieties.

The Fiber Morphology of Kenafindo 1 Agribun and Kenafindo 2 Agribun

The quality of the raw material product can be assessed from its morphology and characteristics. Data on the characteristics of Kenafindo 1 and 2 Agribun fibers are presented in Table 1. In 2017, the Indonesian Research Institute for Sweeteners and Fiber Crops released two new superior varieties of kenaf namely Kenafindo 1 Agribun and Kenafindo 2 Agribun. Kenafindo 1 Agribun variety is the result of a cross between a clone (G4 x KK60) x G4 continued with pedigree selection (SK Release of Kenafindo Variety 1 Agribun, 2017). While the Kenafindo 2 Agribun variety is the result of mass selection in the population IDN-09-HCAN-1272 (SK Release of the 2nd Agribun Kenafindo Variety, 2017).

Table 1. The fiber characteristics of Kenafindo 1 Agribun and Kenafindo 2 Agribun

Parameter	Value	
	Kenafindo 1 Agribun	Kenafindo 2 Agribun
Fiber grade	A	A
Fiber color	White	White
Fiber length (cm)	260 - 375	255-370
Fiber strength (g/tex)	22,19 – 28,89 (very good)	22,96 – 29,36 (very good)
Fiber glossy	Glossy	Glossy
Dirt	little	little
Fiber smooth	Smooth	Smooth
Fiber yield (%)	5 – 7	5 – 7
Potential yield (ton/ha)	2,75 – 4,50	2,50 – 4,50

Source : SK Pelepasan Varietas Kenafindo 1 dan 2 Agribun, 2017

According to Ciptandi (2014) in Hapidh (2017), kenaf fiber is divided into three grades, which can be seen from the characteristics of each fibers. The following are the types of kenaf fibers, including:

- a. Grade A grade kenaf fiber, special fiber quality (good). The A-grade-kenaf fiber has the characteristics of soft, shiny, clean from gum/sap, easy to decompose, brilliant white color and completely clean from dirt.
- b. Grade-B kenaf fiber, good quality fiber. This B-grade kenaf fiber has the characteristics of fibers that have good softness and luster, still contain little gum / sap, are relatively difficult to decipher, dull white, and sufficient fiber cleanliness.
- c. Grade C kenaf fiber, poor quality fiber. This C-grade kenaf fiber has the characteristics of coarse and rigid fibers because it mixes with the bark which is not perfectly processed when retted, tangle, hard to decipher, brittle, blackish brown and dirty.

Kenafindo 1 and 2 Agribun fibers have grade A quality and are white, so the quality of this fiber is very good and is suitable to be used as a thread for textile raw materials. In terms of physical appearance, kenaf fiber has a glossy luster and fine fibers. Kenaf fiber also contains a small amount of impurities. Therefore, kenaf fiber is potential to be used as textile raw material. Based on the research of Ciptandi et al., (2014) the quality of grade A kenaf fibers has a homogeneous filament length. Data on the physical properties of kenaf fibers are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Mechanical property of kenaf fiber

Standard quality	Quality of kenaf fiber	Reference
Tensile strength	240-930 MPa	Alias et al., 2018/ (Ciptandi et al., 2014)
Softness	5 – 10 denier	Ciptandi et al., 2014
Elongation	Max 5 %	Ciptandi et al., 2014
Fibre Denier	14-33	Franck, 2005
Tenacity	2.4-3.33 (g/d)	Ramarad, 2008
Breaking elongation	1.6 %	Franck, 2005
Moisture regain	10-20 %	Yu et.al, 2010

Based on Table 2, kenaf fibers have a tensile strength of 240-930 MPa (5-15 g / tex) and this tensile strength is almost similar to cotton fiber which is 287-597 MPa (18 g / tex) (Alias et al., 2018 ; Wakelyn et al., 2006). The strength of fiber is the energy needed to break a bundle of fiber in the size of one unit with a stelometer which is expressed in the ratio between the strength at breaking and stretching. Fiber strength is expressed as gram per tex. One tex unit is the weight of 1000 m of fiber expressed in grams. The strength of fiber (cotton fiber) received by the textile industry is at least 28 g / tex, (Abdurrahman, 2012). The strength of Kenafindo 1 and 2 fibers is ranging from 22.19 - 29.36 g / tex (Table 1), so most likely it can be accepted in textile industry.

Softness or smoothness of fiber is expressed in denier units. The size of the filament yarns is determined as denier, which is expressed in terms of weight per unit length. If 9000 meters of yarn weigh 1 gm, it is counted as 1 denier. In this system, the unit of length remains constant. The finer the yarn, the smaller the number (Commercial Garment Technology, 2016). The elongation of cotton is expressed as percent elongation taken at the point of breaking, hence the term elongation at break. For most cotton, elongation at break, or just elongation, ranges from 6–9%. The effect of moisture is most pronounced on elongation. An elongation of about 5% at low relative humidity will increase to about 10% when the relative humidity is almost at the saturation point (Wakelyn et al., 2006). The kenaf fiber elongation is 5% which is similar to cotton fiber.

Tenacity is a textile parameter that is related to the strength of a textile material. The smaller the size, the fiber strength is higher, then the fiber is said to have high tenacity (Wahyudi et al., 2015). The absorption (moisture regain) of kenaf fiber is quite high (10-20%), higher than cotton fiber which is only 8%. This higher absorbency makes flax more able to absorb body fluids such as sweat when used as raw material for apparel textiles (Novarini and Mochammad, 2015). Moisture regain is a characteristic index of moisture absorption ability in air (humidity), which also reflects the characteristics of fiber structure. The amount of moisture regain is very important because it deals with the comfort of a textile material (Wahyudi et al., 2015).

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Chemical Characteristics of The Fiber of Kenafindo 1 Agribun and Kenafindo 2 Agribun

The chemical characteristics of fiber are basic information required for using natural fibers in industrial fields. This relates to fiber-based products or diversification of fiber products, which is needed in the manufacturing process data regarding these characteristics, including their potency as textile raw materials (Nurnasari and Nurindah, 2017). The characteristics or chemical properties of natural fibers derive from plants, including hemicellulose, cellulose, lignin, and extractive substances. Table 3 shows the chemical characteristics of kenaf fibers. The composition of these substances generally varies greatly depending on the type or variety of kenaf fibers.

Table 3. Chemical characteristics of Kenafindo 1 Agribun and Kenafindo 2 Agribun

Parameter	Value		
	Kenafindo 1 Agribun	Kenafindo 2 Agribun	Cotton*
Water content (%)	8.36	7.73	8.0**
Ash (%)	0.84	0.74	1.42
Solubility in hot water (%)	1.36	1.91	4.44
Solubility in cold water (%)	0,29	0,70	3.48
Solubility in NaOH (%)	11,62	11,64	5.22
Solubility in Alkohol-Benzena (%)	0.30	1.15	1.66
Lignin (%)	9.36	7.26	-
α -cellulose	63,29	62,78	98.06
Holocellulose	95,94	93,97	93.34
Hemicellulose	32,65	31,19	-

Source : *(Nurnasari and Nurindah, 2017); **(Sukardan et al., 2016)

The water content of Kenafindo 1 and 2 fibers is quite high, 8.36 and 7.73%, respectively, when compared to the water content of cotton fiber which is 8.00%. Fiber that has quite high moisture content affect the nature of the yarn or textile produced. Fiber with high water content will have good comfort when used. In addition, fiber also has good conductivity and absorption capacity for water vapor (Sukardan et al., 2016). The low water levels may result in decreased fiber strength and easily broken fibers, which then reduce fiber length (Moerdoko et al., 1973; Saroso and Darmono, 2002). Kenafindo 1 and 2 fibers have quite high moisture content so that they have almost the same quality as cotton fibers. It means that they are potential to be used as textile raw materials.

The solubility of fiber in hot water, cold water, NaOH and alcohol-benzene is the extractive content of fiber. Extractive content is the result of the secondary metabolic processes of plants which depend on the type, place of growth and climate. Components that are dissolved in cold water are tannins, gums, carbohydrates and pigments. Whereas those dissolved in hot water are the same as those dissolved in cold water plus starch component. Soluble substances in alcohol-benzene are resins, fats, waxes and tannins. Soluble substances in NaOH are lignin, pentosan and hexane (Fatriasari & Hermiati 2008). Extractive substances have an important role in the nature of wood such as natural durability, color and odor (Nurnasari and Nurindah, 2017). The solubility of kenaf fibers in hot and cold water is lower than cotton fibers, this indicates that the amount of solutes such as tannins, gums, carbohydrates, pigments and starch contained in kenaf fibers is lower than cotton fiber.

The content of natural fibers generally consists of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. Cellulose and lignin are among the criteria that show the strength of fiber. Cellulose in composing cell walls is not in the form of a single molecule but in the form of bonds of around 36 molecules of cellulose joined by hydrogen bonds forming a beam of elementary fibrils, and elementary fibrils combine to form linear crystals called microfibrils. Microfibrils combine to form fibrils and eventually cellulose fibers are formed (Sjostrom 1993). Lignin increases the resistance of the wall to pressure and prevents cellulose microfibrils from folding. Cotton fiber does not contain lignin because cotton fibers are pure cellulose

and are classified as fruit fibers while kenaf fibers are classified as stem fibers which contain lignin (7.26 and 9.36%).

2.2. Method

The Use of Kenaf Fiber as Textile Raw Materials

Textile raw materials derived from natural fibers are currently still dominated by cotton fibers which belong to the fruit fiber group. The group of stem fibers is still not widely used for textile raw materials and most are still mixed materials, such as a mixture of kenaf fiber and cotton, or hemp fiber. The application of stem fibers (bast fiber) is for the needs of textiles and textile products (TPT), among others, for textiles (napkins, fabrics, handbags, clothing, denim, socks), technical textiles (ropes, mines, nets, canvas bags, tarps, carpets, geotextiles) (Novarini and Mochammad, 2015).

Kenaf fibers are produced when the core of the kenaf is separated from the fibrous outer layers. Kenaf fibers tend to be stiff because of the lignin content. In order to convert kenaf fibers into a fiber for valuable textile products, the fibers must be either chemically or microbiologically retted (Bel-Berger et al., 1999). Retting aims to eliminate components that attach fibers, such as pectin, hemicellulose, lignin, and other impurities without damaging cellulose fibers (Yu and Yu, 2010; Jamil. H and Marjani, 2018).

There are several methods for retting kenaf bars, including wet retting and dew retting. Wet retting is carried out by soaking the kenaf stems in water. Wet retting has several disadvantages, such as requiring large amounts of water and producing waste that can pollute the environment because it causes foul odors (Tahir et al., 2011) and methane gas from the anaerobic respiration process (Banik et al. 1993; Jamil. H and Marjani, 2018). The second retting method is dew retting which is the process of retting by placing plant stems on the land and letting the original microorganisms grow, especially filamentous fungi (Jamil. H and Marjani, 2018).

Kenaf fiber, when used directly as a textile raw material, produce a rigid yarn so it needs to be mixed with cotton fiber with a certain ratio to produce finer and stronger fibers. Bast fibers, such as linen and ramie, are typically blended with cotton to improve fabric hand (Cheekand Roussel, 1989). Kenaf has a good potency to become an excellent source of fiber in the manufacturing of pulp, paper, and other textile products (Ramaswamy et al., 1995). Kenaf should be potential in the textile industry in manufacturing fabrics like the ramie/cotton blends (Ramaswamy and Easter, 1997).

After retting, the kenaf fiber is processed with the mercerization method. Mercerization is the treatment of fabrics or yarns, with an alkali. The alkali causes the fiber walls to swell and become round, thus increasing in strength, luster, and absorbency. Mercerization also enhances dyeability of cellulosic fibers (Zhang, 2003).

Previous studies showed that the composition of the mixture of kenaf fiber and cotton is 70% cotton and 30% kenaf. The composition of cotton fibers should not exceed 30% because the resulting yarn decreases in strength and is more rigid (Zhang, 2003). The characteristics of kenaf fiber are long, strong, good elasticity, shiny, and broken white color, so that it has the potential to be used in the

textile sector to be further developed into textile raw materials and textile products that have functional and aesthetic values (Hapidh, 2017).

The next steps of using kenaf fiber into textile raw material are weaving (scouring), bleaching, softening, and continued by the spinning process. Based on the results of research by Indriani and Widiawati (2013), the spun kenaf fiber has a regular shape and size even though there are still fine fibers from the fiber. Kenaf fiber is potential to become textile raw material because it can be used as a thread through a spinning process. The form of kenaf fiber is filamentous, so, without spinning, the plant fibers can be directly used as threads, but it is only slightly stiff. Kenaf fiber is also suitable to be used as accessories for fashion products such as bags.

3. Conclusion

Kenaf fiber Kenafindo 1 and Kenafindo 2 varieties have the potential to become textile raw materials for garments. There are several advantages for using kenaf fiber as textile raw materials including good absorption, fire resistance and antimicrobial properties. Previous studies showed that the optimal composition of the mixture of kenaf fiber and cotton is 70% cotton and 30% kenaf.

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